

Performance Development of an Electrical Substation: Monitoring and Controlling using LabVIEW and Fuzzy Logic Controller

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Abstract—Monitoring and controlling substation switching circuits, such as isolators, circuit breakers, and relays, along with temperature detection, can significantly reduce human intervention in hazardous zones. Utilizing a virtual instrument interface through LabVIEW enhances efficiency and safety. Remote accessibility via SMS is facilitated using GSM technology, allowing real-time alerts. Substation equipment status and metering signals are transmitted to the control system via ZigBee. Additionally, a fuzzy logic-based power theft prevention mechanism is implemented by comparing the total load supplied by the transformer with the consumer's usage. This discrepancy helps detect power theft effectively.

Keywords: PowerStation, LabVIEW, Fuzzy Controller, ZigBee, Power Theft Prevention

1. INTRODUCTION

A substation is a critical component in the electrical generation, transmission, and distribution network. It serves functions such as voltage transformation between high transmission voltages and lower distribution levels. Historically, substations evolved as smaller power generation facilities transitioned to distribution hubs connected to larger plants. The rise of modern grids has enhanced their role.

1.1 Zigbee S1 module

ZigBee is a low-power digital communication standard based on IEEE 802, designed for personal area networks. It supports mesh networking, enabling data to traverse multiple devices to extend range. Applications range from wireless light switches and traffic systems to industrial automation. ZigBee's simplicity and efficiency make it an ideal choice over alternatives like Bluetooth for secure and low-rate data transmission.

1.2 LabVIEW

LabVIEW (Laboratory Virtual Instrumentation Engineering Workbench) is a graphical programming platform for industrial and educational automation. Its intuitive interface allows for the creation of control systems and data visualization, offering extensive compatibility with various hardware and communication protocols, such as OPC and Modbus.

1.3. Graphical Programming

LabVIEW ties the creation of user interfaces (called front panels) into the development cycle. LabVIEW programs/subroutines are called virtual instruments (VIs). Each VI has three components: a block diagram, a front panel and connector panel. The last is used to represent the VI in the block diagrams of other, calling VIs. Controls and indicators on the front panel allow an operator to input data into or extract data from a running virtual instrument. However, the front panel can also serve as a programmatic interface. Thus a virtual instrument can either be run as a program, with the front panel serving as a user interface, or, when dropped as a node onto the block diagram, the front panel defines the inputs and outputs for the given node through the connector panel. This implies each VI can be easily tested before being embedded as a subroutine into a larger program.

1.4 Serial Communications

The Xbee-PRO OEM RF Modules interface to a host device through a logic-level asynchronous serial port. Through its serial

Fig. 1.1 System Data Flow Diagram in a UART

port, the module can communicate with any logic and voltage compatible UART; or through a level translator to any serial device (For example: Through a Max-Stream proprietary RS-232 or USB interface board).

Devices that have a UART interface can connect directly to the pins of the RF module as shown in the figure 1.1. Data enters the module UART through the DI pin (pin 3) as an asynchronous serial signal. The signal should idle high when no data is being transmitted. Each data byte consists of a start bit (low), 8 data bits (least significant bit first) and a stop bit (high). The following figure illustrates the serial bit pattern of data passing through the module. The module UART performs tasks, such as timing and parity checking, that are needed for data communications. Serial

communications depend on the two UARTs to be configured with compatible settings (baud rate, parity, start bits, stop bits, data bits). The paper [1] discussed about the power stabilization system using fuzzy logic control type-2. The paper [2] describes about the power systems- classification, detection of fault using fuzzy logic. The paper [3] discussed about industrial wireless automation control with secured process. The paper [4] described about Wireless networks with sensor power system monitoring using fuzzy logic controller. Optimize the performance of substation using microcontroller with sensors [5]. The paper [6] discussed about monitoring the performance using software with the help of transformer oil temperature and control operations. This paper [7] dealt with failure in substation occurs the message sends to the substation maintenance officers automatically. The paper [8] discussed with power exchanged over some distances for improving the quality of electrical power. The paper [9] implemented and tested the voltage level of all the components used In the substations and also invented the faults. This [10] paper discussed the effective foundation method for substations safety status.

initializes serial communication parameters, such as baud rate (default: 9600) and data bits (default: 8). Error handling ensures stable operation.

Fig 3.1 VISA Configure Serial Port

- VISA resource name -Specifies the resource to be opened. This control also Fig
- specifies the session and class.
- Baud Rate – It is the rate of transmission. The default is 9600.
- Data bits- It is the number of bits in the incoming data. The value of data bits is between five and eight. The default value is 8.
- Parity- Specifies the parity used for every frame to be transmitted or received. This input accepts the following values.
- Stop bits -Specifies the number of stop bits used to indicate the end of a frame. This input accepts the following values.
- Flow control -Sets the type of control used by the transfer mechanism.

2. BLOCK DIAGRAM

The substation monitoring system uses LabVIEW to process inputs from ZigBee modules interfaced with substation equipment. The control signals generated by the system trigger actions via a PIC microcontroller. Fault detection data is relayed to the control room and, in critical cases, sent to a user’s mobile via GSM is shown in the figure 2.1

The functional block diagram illustrates data flow from sensors to control mechanisms and communication modules.

Fig 2.1 Functional Block Diagram

3. LABVIEW DESIGN

3.1 VISA Configure Serial Port

3.1 VISA Configure Serial Port This module

3.2. Property Node

Property Node Property Nodes in LabVIEW adapt to the class of referenced objects, allowing dynamic configuration of VISA,.NET, and ActiveX properties.

3.3 VISA Read

FL Load Fuzzy System VI This module loads predefined fuzzy logic rules from a .fs file for system control. Absolute paths ensure correct file referencing.

Fig.3.2 VISA Read Source

3.4. VISA Write

Writes the data from write buffer to the device or interface specified by VISA resource name is shown in the figure 3.3.

Fig. 3.3 VISA Write Source

3.5 VISA Resource Name:

Fig. 3.4 VISA Resource Name

- VISA resource name specifies the resource to be opened. The VISA resource name control also specifies the session and class.
- Write buffer contains the data to be written to the device
- Error in describes error conditions that occur before this node runs. This input provides standard error in functionality.
- VISA resource name out is a copy of the VISA resource name that VISA functions return.
- Return count contains the actual number of bytes written.
- Error out contains error information. This output provides standard error out functionality.

3.6. FL Load Fuzzy System VI

Loads a fuzzy system from a .fs file. Use the FL Save Fuzzy System VI to save the .fs file after you make any modifications. You also can load and save .fs files in the Fuzzy System Designer.

File path specifies the path to the .fs file. You must specify an absolute path. If you specify an empty or relative path, this VI returns an error.

Fuzzy system out returns the complete information for a fuzzy system. Wire the fuzzy system out output of this VI to the fuzzy system in input of another VI is shown in the figure

single-output (MISO) fuzzy system[2] is shown in the figure 3.5.

Fig 3.7. FL Fuzzy Controller (MISO)

Fuzzy system in specifies the complete information for a fuzzy system. Wire the fuzzy system out output from another VI to the fuzzy system in input of this VI.

Input values specifies the values of the input variables in the fuzzy system. The fuzzy logic

controller evaluates the output value(s) according to the input values and the rules of the fuzzy system.

Output value returns the value of the output variable in the fuzzy system. The fuzzy logic controller evaluates the output value according to the input value(s) and the rules of the fuzzy system. If output value is zero, use the rule-zero or if the fuzzy logic controller did not invoke any rule to evaluate the output variable is shown in the figure.

Rule weights returns the rule weights that the fuzzy logic controller uses to scale the membership functions of the output linguistic variables is shown in the figure.

Block diagram objects include terminals, subVIs, functions, constants, structures, and wires, which transfer data among other block diagram objects. After you create the front panel window, you add code using graphical representations of functions to control the front panel objects. The block diagram window contains this graphical source code is shown in the figure. 3.6.

Fig 3.5 LabVIEW Front panel

The front panel contains controls and indicators, which are the interactive input and output terminals of the VI, respectively. Controls are knobs, push buttons, dials, and other input devices. Indicators are graphs, LEDs, and other displays.

Controls simulate instrument input devices and supply data to the block diagram of the VI. Indicators simulate instrument output devices and display data the block diagram acquires or generates.

Fuzzy Inputs and Rules Input variables, such as voltage and load, are converted into fuzzy sets using membership functions. Fuzzy control rules simulate scenarios to mitigate theft, e.g., over-voltage conditions trigger specific corrective actions.

Fig 3.6 Block diagram

4. FUZZY CONTROLLER TO PREVENT POWER THEFT

4.1 Principle of Preventing Power Theft Prevention

4.1 Principle of Operation Power theft detection relies on comparing energy supplied by the transformer with the total consumer usage. Discrepancies beyond permissible losses indicate theft than the consumer’s meter reading, then it is the case of power theft. Using this error signal we can detect the power theft [5].

4.3 Fuzzy Control rules

If the load (in MW) becomes positive, then it’s the case of power theft. Therefore the rule for prevention of power theft is simulated.

“If the load (L_i) is zero and the voltage (V_i) is mf13 then change voltage is mf3”. This is the case of over-voltage. Similarly other rules can be framed from the rule table is shown in the figure. 4.3

Fig 4.2: Fuzzy Logic Rules

5. Simulation and Hardware Results

5.1 Fuzzy Result

Fig4.1: Fuzzy inputs and output

Fig5.1: Fuzzy Result

4.2 Fuzzy inputs and output

5.2 Proteus Result

Fig.5.2. Proteus Result

Figure 5.2 Hardware Setup The hardware implementation confirms real-world functionality, with critical failures triggering alerts and protective actions

6. HARDWARE OUTPUT

Fig.6.1 Hardware output shows the substation Monitoring

Fig. 6.2. Hardware output

6. RESULT ANALYSIS

The set point given for the overload is 45 °c and fire accident is 70 °c in the front panel of the LabVIEW application from the substation control unit .

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Table 1: Result Analysis of hardware output

Temperature Measured	Buzzer	Isolation	Message
30 (normal)	Off	Line 1/ line 2	Off
50 (over load)	Beep	Alternate Line	Overload warning message
80 (fire accident)	On	Shutdown	Fire accident message

Table 1 shows substation overload monitoring and controlling using fuzzy controller. If the setpoint is above 80 degree gives the buzzer ON, the fire accident message sent and it shut down the substation.

8. CONCLUSION

The integration of LabVIEW and Fuzzy for substation monitoring minimizes Human exposure to hazardous Zones while enabling efficient fault detection and power theft prevention . Future improvements may focus on enabling data transmission security and system scalability.

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